

Synthesis of some New Chromeno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine Derivatives

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Literature reports the syntheses of benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives by the reaction of 3-amino-2-carbomethoxybenzofuran with urea and formamide¹, many pyranopyrimidines by the reaction of heterocyclic β -enamino ester², and pyrano[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines by the reaction of nitriles with heterocyclic active methylene compounds, viz. thiobarbituric acid³. Tricyclic heterocyclic systems derived from tetrahydrobenzofurans have also been reported⁴. In the light of hitherto discussion on fused pyrimidines with oxygen heterocycles, it was thought of interest to use the chromene ester (**1**) to construct the pyrimidine nucleus fused at C(2) and C(3) positions of the chromene ring system. The crystal structure of the chromene ester (**1**) has recently been reported⁵.

Synthesis of chromenopyrimidines has been carried out by the reaction of **1** with urea, thiourea and formamide. The products obtained have been found to be accompanied by eliminations in the side-chain. Esters with β -hydrogen are known to undergo thermal elimination⁶ giving alkenes. They are also known to activate the α -hydrogen and favour thermal elimination leading to the formation of α,β -unsaturated esters⁷. Derivatives of chromene with an exocyclic double bond have been reported⁸. The driving force for elimination seems to be the formation of a conjugated double bond in which the exocyclic carbon has electron-withdrawing groups resulting the formation of a linearly fused tricyclic system. The experimental conditions employed in this work corresponded to those reported in the literature¹, which involve mixing the equimolar quantities of the reactants and heating at higher temperatures. No acidic or basic reagents were used.

Reaction of salicylaldehyde with two equivalents of ethyl cyanoacetate afforded 2-amino-3-carbomethoxy-4-(1-carbomethoxy-1-nitrimethyl)4[*H*]chromene⁹ (**1**). Reaction of **1** with urea, thiourea and formamide carried out with a view to construct the pyrimidine ring fused to C(2) to C(3) positions of the chromene nucleus, gave the corresponding compounds **2-4** (Scheme 1).

When the above sequence of reactions was carried out on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, 2-amino-3-carbomethoxy-4-(1-carbomethoxy-1-nitrimethyl)-5,6-benzo-4*H*-chromene (**1a**) was obtained. The product obtained in the reaction of **1a** with urea was characterized as **2a** indicating the elimination of HCN, which was supported by the absence of $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ band at 2250 cm^{-1} . The reaction of **1a** with thiourea resulted in the formation of **3a** which was accompanied by dehydrogenation. The product obtained in the reaction of

1a with formamide was consistent with structure **4**. Formation of the exocyclic double bond in structures **2**, **3**, **4**, **3a** and **4a** was also supported by the presence of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band around 2200 cm^{-1} , whereas in **1** and **1a** the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency was observed around 2250 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken on a Buchi apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian 300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-(1-carbomethoxy-1-nitrimethylene)chromeno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (2): A mixture of chromene ester (**1**; 1 g, 0.003 mol) and urea (0.36 g, 0.006 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath, then cooled and washed with water. The solid separated was crystallized from DMF-water, (75%), m.p. 268° (Found: C, 60.01; H, 3.53; N, 13.12. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$ calcd. for: C, 59.07; H, 3.38; N, 12.92%; ν_{max} 2200 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1700 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 3200 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 1.2 (3H, t, CH_3), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH_2), 7.4–7.8 (4H, m, ArH), 8.4–9.00 (2H, br, NH).

2-Mercapto-4-hydroxy-5-(1-carbomethoxy-1-nitrimethylene)chromeno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (3): A mixture of chromene ester (**1**; 1 g, 0.003 mol) and thiourea (0.45 g, 0.006 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath, then cooled and washed with water. The solid separated was crystallized from DMF-water, (80%), m.p. 273° (Found: C, 56.82; H, 3.41; N, 12.52. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}_6$ calcd.

for : C, 56.30; H, 3.23; N, 12.31%; ν_{\max} 2200 (C≡N), 1680 and 1700 (C=O), 3400 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂), 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 8.5–9.0 (2H, br, NH).

4-Hydroxy-5-(1-nitriomethylene)chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (4) : A mixture of chromene ester (1; 1 g, 0.003 mol) and formamide (0.3 ml, 0.006 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath, then cooled and poured in ice-cold water. The separated solid was crystallized from DMF-water, (82%), m.p. 263° (Found : C, 66.02; H, 3.12; N, 17.60. C₁₃H₇N₃O₂ calcd. for : C, 65.82; H, 2.95; N, 17.72%); ν_{\max} 2210 (C≡N), 1710 (C=O), 3400 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 7.4–7.8 (4H, m, ArH), 8.8 and 8.9 (C2-H of pyrimidine, CHCN, NH).

2-Amino-3-carbethoxy-4-(1-carbethoxy-1-nitriomethyl)-5,6-benzo-4[H]chromene (1a) : To a mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1 g, 0.007 mol) and ethyl cyanoacetate (1.6 ml, 0.014 mol), catalytic amount of piperidine was added, then kept in an ice chest for 4 h. The solid separated was washed with cold ethanol and crystallized from ethanol, (73%), m.p. 135° (Found : C, 66.74; H, 4.96; N, 7.12. C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 66.31; H, 5.26; N, 7.36%); ν_{\max} 2246 (C≡N), 1740, 1665 (C=O), 3456, 3320 cm^{-1} (NH).

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-(1-carbethoxymethylene)-6,7-benzochromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (2a) : A mixture of benzochromene ester (1a; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) and urea (0.31 g, 0.0052 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath, then cooled and washed with water. The separated solid was crystallized from ethanol, (78%), m.p. 268° (Found : C, 64.89; H, 3.23; N, 7.68. C₁₉H₁₄N₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 65.14; H, 4.00; N, 8.00%); ν_{\max} 1730, 1700, 1660 (C=O), 3390 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, q, OCH₂), 8.3 (1H, s, CHCOOC₂H₅), 8.2 and 8.8 (NH), 7.1–7.95 (6H, m, ArH).

2-Mercapto-4-hydroxy-5-(1-carbethoxy-1-nitriomethylene)-6,7-benzochromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (3a) : A mixture of benzochromene ester (1a; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) and thiourea (0.4 g, 0.0052 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath. It was then cooled and washed with water. The separated solid was crystallized from ethanol, (78%), m.p. 250° (Found : C, 60.89; H, 3.52; N, 10.05. C₂₆H₁₃N₃O₄S calcd. for : C, 61.38; H, 3.32; N, 10.74%); ν_{\max} 2200 (C≡N), 1665 and 1730 (C=O), 3385 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.3 (2H, q, OCH₂), 7.5–8.4 (4H, m, ArH), 8.9 and 9.4 (2H, br, NH).

4-Hydroxy-5-(1-nitriomethylene)-6,7-benzochromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (4a) : A mixture of benzochromene ester (1a; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) and formamide (0.234 g, 0.0052 mol) was heated for 4 h at 150–60° in an oil-bath, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The separated solid was crystallized from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 256° (Found : C, 69.83; H, 3.02; N, 14.50. C₁₇H₉N₃O₂ calcd. for : C, 70.58; H, 3.11; N, 14.53%); ν_{\max} 2210 (C≡N), 1705 (C=O), 3370 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 8.2 and 8.6 (2H, s, =CHCH and C2-H of pyrimidine moiety), 7.00–7.55 (6H, m, ArH).

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